

MULTITEMPORAL ANALYSIS OF LAND USE AND COVER HISTORY OF THE MACABU RIVER BASIN (RIO DE JANEIRO – BR)

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RESUMO – As bacias hidrográficas são importantes unidades de análise para o planejamento ambiental da sociedade, pois estas traduzem de forma sistêmica as características da paisagem fluvial. O uso da terra, nessas bacias, vem sendo modificado continuamente ao longo dos anos. Dessa forma, este estudo analisou a área da bacia do rio Macabu, seu uso e cobertura da terra a fim de demonstrar o seu histórico de usos e ocupação de 1984 até o ano de 2018, baseado em mapeamentos prévios de instituições renomadas e na análise das imagens do satélite Sentinel-2. Os resultados desse estudo demonstraram que em 1984, o alto curso fluvial era caracterizado por suas florestas, o baixo e médio curso eram caracterizados pela agricultura, após 35 anos, boa parte desses usos deu lugar à pastagem da pecuária extensiva que se fixou na região. Também houve a supressão de 60% da floresta da bacia, majoritariamente por áreas de pastagem. Constatou-se que as áreas urbanas expandiram em mais de 100% em relação a 1984. A supressão da floresta, a expansão da pecuária e a degradação do solo trazem consequências inegáveis ao aporte de sedimentos transportados pelos rios e à degradação das feições geomorfológicas da bacia do rio Macabu.

ABSTRACT – Drainage basin is an important analysis unit in the society's environmental planning; hence it systematically translates the fluvial landscape characteristics. Land use is continuously changing land cover. In this way, this study analyzed the Macabu river basin based on land use and land coverage mapping to identify its previous use and how the usage changed between 1984 and 2018, based on previous mappings by prominent institutions and Sentinel-2 satellite imagery. The results of this study showed that in 1984, the upper stream was characterized by forests, the middle and lower stream were previous used for agriculture, past 35 years, a huge part of these uses changed into pasture because of the extensive cattle fixed in the drainage basin. In addition, there was also the suppression of 60% of the basins' forest area into pastures. It was found that the cities developed over 100% in relation to 1984. The forest suppression in upper stream, agrobusiness and cattle expansion in middle stream and the ground degradation in low stream, those processes undoubtedly bring tremendous consequences to river sediments transportation and degradation of geomorphological features in Macabu river basin.

1 INTRODUCTION

Land use is any activity and structure made by humans that can transform its cover, that is, any activity directly related to the soil (PRAKASAM, 2010). Every day, land use is more intense, and this is reflected in the change in its cover. The identification of land use and land cover in river basins contributes to the environmental history of river functioning, in addition to assisting in analyses related to the connectivity of sediment transport among river environments (BRIERLY; FRYIRS, 2013; MARÇAL; LIMA, 2016; DUARTE; MARÇAL, 2017).

Christofoletti (1988) defines a river basin as an area that drains water, sediments, and dissolved materials into a common channel. This geomorphological unit is crucial for spatial analyses and has increasingly required multidisciplinary studies to address water issues, both as a shaping agent of the landscape and as a vital resource for society (BOWMAN, 2023).

The identification and analysis of land uses within a river basin are critically important. Economic activities frequently contribute to the sedimentation and pollution of river channels (GHOSH et al, 2022). This is particularly

evident when such activities result in mass movements and soil erosion, which can significantly alter the dynamics of rivers.

Therefore, the objective of this study is to present the changes in land use between 1984 and 2018 in the Macabu River basin, in the state of Rio de Janeiro. This study aims to contribute to the management of the basin and to the understanding of the environmental history of the Macabu River basin, with its occupations and transformations. (GBENGA ABAYOMI AFUYE et al, 2024; DE QUEIROZ et al, 2025; BIKIS et al, 2025). The analysis will be conducted in a river basin with clearly defined courses to ensure an understandable interpretation of the results (BOWMAN, 2023).

The Macabu River basin has an area of 1,108 km², within the coordinates: 21°57'27.60"S 41°26'53.42"W; 22°3'5.40"S 41°24'0.49"W; 22°0'26.74"S 41°51'59.22"W and 22°18'23.88"S 42°15'32.44"W (PRADO, et al, 2004), crossing the municipal limits of Campos dos Goytacazes, Carapebus, Conceição de Macabu, Macaé, Quissamã, Santa Maria Madalena and Trajano de Moraes, in the northern region of the State of Rio de Janeiro (Figure 1).

Heilbron, Eirado and Almeida (2016) say that the upper course of this basin contains rocks of the Paraíba do Sul Complex (garnet-biotite-sillimanite gneisses), while the lower course, near Lagoa Feia, includes various types of river-lagoon and wind deposits composed mainly of quartz gravel and sand (PEREIRA; FERNANDO, 2020; KISS et al, 2023). Approximately 31% of the basin's area consists of mountainous regions covered by the Atlantic Forest (PRADO, et al., 2004; WEST; MELLO, 2020). According to Bastos & Napoleão (2011), the basin currently has 61% of fields and/or pasture areas.

Figure 1 – Location of the Macabu River basin.

Source: Author's (2019)

2 METHODOLOGY

The research comprised an initial bibliographic study of the area in question and employed land use and land cover mapping as a crucial analytical tool to identify the historical usage patterns of the basin. The time frame of the research is 35 years, so the data analyzed covers the period between 1984 and 2018. Based on free images from the Sentinel-2 satellite (USGS, 2018) and using geoprocessing tools, a reinterpretation of land use and land cover mapping in the state of Rio de Janeiro was carried out, which had already been done by renowned institutions (INEA, 2017; IBGE, 2014, and Mappiomas Brasil, 2015). Table 1 lists all the materials used. In total, there were four shapefiles of land use and land

cover maps, which are more current, and three scenes from the Sentinel-2 satellite (Table 1). They were obtained from the USGS Earth Explorer portal (2018).

Table 1 – Raster and vector data used

Material	Reference date or year	Scale/Resolution	Source
Shapefile use and cover IBGE	2014	1:250.000	IBGE, 2014
Shapefile use and cover INEA	2010	1:100.000	INEA, 2017
Raster use and cover	1985	1:100.000	MapBiomass, 2015
	2018	Spatial: 30 meters	
Raster Sentinel images	7/20/2018	Spatial: 10 meters	ESA, 2019
	7/28/2018 (2)	Time: 5 days	

Source: Various sources (see last column).

To download the MapBiomass shapefiles (Collection 3 of the Annual Series of Land Cover and Land Use Maps of Brazil, accessed on June 10, 2019, via the link: <http://mapbiomas.org>), we used the online software Google Engine (free online software). ArcGIS software (student trial license) was used to process and analyze this and other materials and was also used to prepare the maps featured in this study. Subsequently, a shapefile was converted to KML (Keyhole Markup Language) format using QGIS software (free). Google Earth was also used to verify changes in land cover and use.

Using ArcGIS software, the shapefiles were processed for topology correction, attribute table editing, and standardization of all datums and projections to WGS 84 and UTM, respectively.

Images from July 20 and 28, 2018, from the Sentinel-2 satellite. (Table 2). Still in ArcGIS software, they were unified into a single file through editing, based on the 2018 images, updating them. All processed shapefiles of land use and land cover were placed on the Sentinel 2 satellite scenes and matched by resampling points to adjust the higher resolution of Sentinel's image (10m) to shapefile's resolution (30m) and visual analysis to interpret them and find inconsistencies.

Table 2 – Sentinel - 2 satellite spectral bands

Band Number	Band Name	Center Wavelength (nm)	Band Length (nm)
2	Blue	496.6	98
3	Green	560.0	45
4	Red	664.5	38
8	Near Infrared	835.1	145

Source: ESA, 2019 (modified).

When opening the KML in Google Earth, it was possible to verify previous land uses using the "Historical Images" tool. Thus, in this interface, the mapping was edited for the year 1984 to find the expected results. To obtain the previous uses of the Macabu River basin, the 1984 data from the Mapbiomas mapping was analyzed, and the current edited shapefile was placed in Google Earth for remodeling and, to be consistent with the year 1984, using the historical series tool that allows us to reach that date and visual analysis.

The land use and land cover classes for the year 1984 were standardized according to those established for the year 2018. These included: urban areas, agriculture, pasture, and field/pasture for land use classes; and fields, forest, exposed soil, and water body for land cover classes.

The 2018 data were integrated by merging geospatial information (ArcGIS merge tool) and editing the shapefiles on Sentinel-2 images (visual interpretation using infrared for vegetation class analysis) to extract data for the year 2018. In this way, it was possible to compare those results from 2018 with those from 1984, according to Mapbiomas mapping and based on Google Earth images.

3 RESULTS

The results will be presented with a presentation of land use and land cover change for both results, showing what has changed mainly in the upper course region where the Macabu hydroelectric dam is located and the middle course where the city of Conceição de Macabu is located (BOWMAN, 2023). Quantitative results from this research will also be presented in a table of land use and land cover classes.

Based on data from ESA (2017), IBGE (2014), INEA (2017), and Mapbiomas (2015), the following land use and land cover map was obtained for the year 2018 (Figure 2). This mapping categorized land use and land cover into the following classes: urban areas (encompassing the city of Conceição de Macabu and other urban agglomerations),

agriculture (cultivated areas), pasture, field/pasture (a transitional mosaic between these two land uses), field (grassland), forest, exposed soil (including rocky outcrops and sandy ridges), and water bodies (rivers and lakes).

Figure 2 – Land use and land cover map for the year 2018.

Source: Author's (2019).

Using data from MapBiomias Brasil (2015), along with Google Earth and its historical image series tool, the land use and land cover map for the year 1984 (Figure 3) was also produced. The land use and land cover classes for 1984 were standardized according to those developed for 2018.

Figure 3 - Map of land use and land cover for the year 1984.

Source: Author's (2019).

Figure 4 illustrates the areas that experienced changes in land use or land cover during the study period (1984–2018). The same land use and land cover classes were maintained, including agriculture, field/pasture, field, water bodies, forest, pasture, exposed soil, and urban areas.

Additionally, the classification of areas that underwent changes and their respective transitions were identified: agriculture transitioned into a mosaic of agriculture and pasture (representing the integrated use of multiple economic activities within the same geographic space), field/pasture evolved into a mosaic of pasture and field/pasture; field similarly transformed into a mosaic of pasture and field/pasture; pasture converted into exposed soil, indicating soil degradation; forest was altered to field/pasture due to anthropogenic influences on land cover; agriculture and pasture surrounding urban agglomerations shifted to urban areas, contributing to their expansion; and forest was modified into a mosaic of pasture and agriculture.

Figure 4 - Comparison between the results of land use and land cover change and unchanged

Source: Author's (2019).

Based on these spatial data, quantitative metrics were extracted (Table 3) to illustrate the changes occurring in the Macabu River basin over three decades (1984 to 2018).

Table 3 – Results of the mapping of land use and land cover change in percentage (%) compared to the total area of the Macabu river basin

CLASSES	1984		2018		Area Change (km ²)	Percentage of change
	Area (km ²)	Percentage of total area	Area (km ²)	Percentage of total area		
Agriculture	32,64	2,95%	45,18	4,08%	12,54	38,42%
Urban area	2,63	0,24%	5,35	0,48%	2,71	103,36%
Field	10,29	0,93%	6,09	0,55%	-4,2	40,86%
Field/pasture	196,46	17,75%	166,82	15,07%	-29,64	15,09%
Forest	321,46	29,04%	332,77	30,06%	11,3	3,52%
Pasture	538,48	48,64%	539,99	48,78%	1,5	0,28%
Exposed Soil	2,48	0,22%	8,01	0,72%	5,52	222,91%

Source: Author's (2019).

4 DISCUSSION

Based on the results of the land use and land cover mappings, we sought to relate past uses to the activities currently being developed. To achieve this, a map was created to distinguish areas that experienced changes in use and cover from those that remained unchanged between 1984 and 2018. Figure 5 highlights not only the areas where changes in use and cover occurred but also the new classifications resulting from these transformations.

Figure 5 – Map identifying changes in the land use and land cover in the Macabu River basin.

Source: Author's (2019).

The forest class underwent substantial changes during the study period, transitioning into areas of field/pasture as a result of the expansion of extensive cattle ranching (Figure 5, indicated in light green). Similarly, the field class and field/pasture areas were converted to pasture by 2018 (Figure 5, represented in purple and lilac). A portion of the forest class was transformed into a mosaic of agricultural and pasture areas (Figure 5, shown in dark green), while the agriculture class also experienced a change in area to pasture (Figure 5, marked in pink). Areas classified as pasture in 1984 were partly converted to exposed soil in the lower course of the basin (Figure 5, indicated in orange). Additionally, the urban area expanded significantly (103,36%), especially within the municipality of Conceição de Macabu (Figure 5, represented in red).

According to the findings, the middle course of the basin exhibited urbanization and growth of the city of Conceição de Macabu, which now has a population exceeding 27,000 inhabitants, as reported by IBGE (2011). Consequently, the urban area class grew by 103.36% in 2018, as illustrated in Table 3 and Figure 5. Between 1984 and 2018, the cities and towns within the Macabu River basin also doubled in size. Another important aspect to consider is the geomorphology present in this basin. It is possible to observe the occupation of the territory, that is, urban areas according to the relief of the basin, where the population preferred to occupy the river plains near the water sources, and later cultivation and livestock farming occupied the hilly regions of the basin.

The forest class in the basin area experienced an increasing of 11.3 km², from 321.46 km² to 332.77 km², representing only 3.52% of its total area. The importance of the Atlantic Forest remains noteworthy, particularly for the protection of water springs in the upper course (GUEDES PINTO *et al*, 2023). Figure 4 highlights the suppression of forest vegetation, which occurred primarily in the middle and lower courses, near urban and agricultural areas, even though it is proportionally increasing in other parts of the basin. Figure 5 indicates that pasture accounted for the most significant encroachment on forested areas, this observation underscores the increasing expansion of pasture as economic activity in the basin.

The agricultural area within the basin expanded by approximately 12.54 km², primarily occupying lands in the lower course and around the city of Conceição de Macabu. This 38% increase largely resulted from the suppression of pasture, as shown in Figure 5. This transition facilitated the growth of mechanized agribusiness in the lower course, supporting the continuous population growth of surrounding cities.

Pasture remained nearly stable over the 34-year study period, with a negligible growth of only 0.28%. Figure 5 illustrates that most of pasture class was converted to mechanized agriculture (agribusiness), and also replaced by urban

areas, these conversions suggest a downward trend for the pasture class. However, when considering the expansion of pasture farming in the Macabu River basin and the degradation of unproductive cropland that has been converted to pasture, it is possible to outline a scenario for the stability of the pasture area throughout the period studied.

Another significant change was the reduction in the field and field/pasture classes, which decreased by approximately 40% and 15%, respectively (Table 3). As shown in figure 5, the field/pasture class transitioned to the field class, which subsequently experienced a substantial reduction.

Probably, the field/pasture class was likely replaced by exposed soil due to long-term soil degradation. This class consists not only of rocky outcrops but also areas of bare soil and regions with exposed sediments and minerals, such as river-lagoon deposits at the mouth of the Macabu River. Thus, soil degradation in these areas may have led to the loss of grass vegetation, leaving the soil exposed. As a result, this class more than doubled in size, exhibiting a growth rate of 223%.

Overall, the Macabu River basin did not undergo intense urbanization like the major urban centers of the State of Rio de Janeiro. However, its urban areas expanded by more than 100% compared to 1984, accompanied by the growth of cattle ranching and extensive agriculture (GIESEBART, 2022). Additionally, grassland areas experienced a significant process of soil degradation, leading to the formation of exposed soil by 2018 (HOOKE, 2022).

5 CONCLUSION

This study shows that in the period from 1984 to 2018 there were significant changes in land use in the Macabu River basin (SOFFIATI, 2021). The most affected region was the middle course, due to the expansion of the city of Conceição de Macabu and in the areas of agriculture and pasture that supply the city. The high and low courses also suffered from the process of change, although characterized by the expansion of areas of forest and exposed soil, respectively.

In the Macabu River basin, there was a significant increase of 222% in the area of exposed soil. This is probably related to the suppression of the field and the stagnation of pasture areas (0.28% growth), because, in both, the soil is more exposed to weathering and they generally shelter (or have sheltered) activities such as agriculture and pasture, respectively, which are very degrading and impoverish the soil; leaving it unproductive and exposed.

The urban area, without a doubt, has undergone significant changes with an increase of 103% in the entire basin, within the study period. This draws attention to the process of expansion of agribusiness and also the expansion of cities towards rural areas, annexing areas that previously supplied the city with food from small farmers. It is most likely related to the loss of space for the field and the field/pasture, which suffered suppression of 40% and 15%, respectively.

The changes of forest in the upper course, the expansion of agribusiness and cattle ranching in the middle course and the degradation of the land in the lower course, raise the question of how the transport of sediments in this basin is being carried out, since there is less vegetation in its entire area. Therefore, the input of sediments must be constantly being monitored as it is increasing and there is not enough vegetation to regulate the flow of energy along the rivers, so perhaps its transport must be more accelerated, increasingly incisive and losing part of its geomorphological features

This study served to discuss the role of land use and land cover activities on the river system of the Macabu River basin and how the history of changes in land use and land cover in the basin can influence its hydrology and sediment transport (GBENGA ABAYOMI AFUYE et al, 2024). Unfortunately, this study did not have access to data prior to the drainage and straightening works carried out by the government in previous decades, which remains an open question for future work. However, this article demonstrates the state of the art in research on land use and land cover mapping for the management of this river basin (DE QUEIROZ et al, 2025; BIKIS et al, 2025).

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